

Human-Computer Analogy: Current Bio-Inspired Approaches to Neural Networks

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Abstract—The human-computer analogy has been often made to compare particular components and functions in a similar fashion between the human brain and modern computers. However, until recently, computers were not adept to simulating the mind in the least. Intuitively, we can compare RAM to short-term memory, hard disk space to long-term memory, a motherboard to physical architecture, and so on. However, computers do not employ crucial aspects of cognition, transfer learning, or the seemingly arbitrary randomness of “intuition”. However, times are changing with newer, parallel, transfer-learning capable neural networks. This paper will provide a general background, discuss some current bio-inspired neural networks that most closely reflect the human brain, along with designing an experiment in ViZDoom to gauge the validity and performance of using Asynchronous Actor-Critic Agents. Further discussion will be given to Progressive Neural Networks, Ternary Neural Networks, and their comparisons with brain processing and memory.

Index Terms—ViZDoom, Reinforcement Learning, Deep Learning, A3C, TNN, ProgNN, Autonomous Systems, Cognition.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Problem Statement

The human-computer analogy is generally attributed to von Neumann (The Computer and the Brain, 1958) in describing the comparisons between the nervous system and a computer. During the same time period (sometimes called the “Cognitive Revolution”), the idea of humans being an “Information Processing Machine” was being developed by Newell and Simon, but more on the cognitive psychology side. Unsurprisingly, both areas were influenced by Turing’s work in the 1940s and 50s. It is a rather intuitive comparison to be made; we both have processing, memory, sensors, an operating system, etc. However, these components and features alone are absolutely insufficient to make any form of meaningful comparison between the human brain (or mind) and a device that emulates human functions via a hardware/software synthesis.

Ever since the reintroduction of neural networks for artificial intelligence after AlexNet’s implementation of *Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)* in 2012, they have been the driving factor for advances in computer vision, natural language processing, and speech recognition. Shortly after, in 2014, *Reinforcement Learning (RL)* demonstrated ground-breaking result using DeepMind’s architecture combining *CNNs* and *Q-Learning* to set record-breaking scores on Atari 2600 games [1]. Creating neural networks simply to beat video games seems a bit of a unique business case, so why would Google pay \$500M USD to acquire DeepMind in 2014 [2]?

This question would ultimately be answered not by the fact that the network can solve such problems, but more as *how* it solves them, i.e., similar to how a human would. “The cognitive processes which the AI goes through are said to be very like those a human who had never seen the game would use to understand and attempt to master it” [3]. Without knowing any of the rules inside a game, the network was able to use reinforcement learning policies to master the game, far better than any human, in just a couple of hours while using the same “trial-and-error” approaches that humans learning when failing at games. Since this time, the agents have been improving and the architectures have been changing in a form that far better represents the human-computer analogy than the original proposition every had.

Information Processing Theory - Computer Analogy

Fig. 1: Human-Computer Analogy in Information Processing [9].

1.2 Why Simulation in Video Games?

Simulation (and emulation) environments are commonly useful to reduce the complexity of real-life. Validation can be conducted in a “perfect world” that is free of external events and states that could interfere with the results trying to be verified (controlled experiment). Previously, classical reinforcement learning methods were being implemented

for computer vision and robotics with a major limitation: a lack of transfer learning. Transfer Learning is the ability of an AI to learn from different tasks and apply its pre-learned knowledge to a completely new task. It is well known that robots are able to master very complex tasks with high proficiency and speed (though they fail at the simplest tasks, which is hoped to be improved with artificial general intelligence). The issue is that this highly specialized robotic device (i.e. KUKA arm for assembling vehicles) can only perform one task... it never learns to apply these techniques elsewhere. For comparison, imagine a human that learned how to play tennis but was utterly incapable of playing a game of badminton even being the "best in class" at a similar sport.

Fig. 2: DeepMind AI in Montezuma’s Revenge [10].

Old video games are ideal because they require low amounts of memory, energy, and time for training trials. The state space is relatively small too, depending on the number of potential actions (inputs). Furthermore, two games can be completely different having no overlapping actions or results which is ideal for testing transfer learning [4]. (This is completed by the final network layer being dense and *not* being shared between different tasks). Finally, it should be self-evident that simulating games is much safer (for both the device/robot and the human) than deploying on hardware that can cost thousands of dollars and result in death or injury of the operator.

Fig. 3: Google DeepMind AI performance exceeding human capabilities [8].

2 THE COMPUTER SIDE

Many components and functions can be compared with human brain counterparts. In this section, the focus is primarily on ANNs and what they provide.

2.1 Background / Previous Work

Historical information about *Q-Learning* will be provided here. Please see the section "Current Algorithms and Architectures" below for current implementations [25].

Q-Learning is a machine learning technique under the umbrella of reinforcement learning. *Deep Q-Learning (DQN)* is a flavor of *Q-learning* that was designed by Google’s DeepMind research group in 2014 [1]. In DeepMind’s patent and research, they showed that machine learning agents were able to learn to play Atari 2600 games at a human equivalence to expert as a result. Since then, *DQN*’s have been used to teach robots to walk, play physical games (like football and ping-pong), as well as complete other tasks in which the robot is "self-taught."

The commonly accepted notation for the *Q-Learning* value iteration update equation is given as:

$$Q^{new}(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow (1-\alpha) \cdot Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha \cdot (r_t + \gamma \cdot \max_a Q(s_{t+1}, a))$$

where:

$Q^{new}(s_t, a_t)$ is the current (new) reward quality as a function of the state, action, and time.

$Q(s_t, a_t)$ is the previous (old) reward quality.

α is the learning rate.

γ is the discount factor.

r_t is the reward value.

$\max_a Q(s_{t+1}, a)$ is the estimation of the optimal future value.

In general, the goal of the agent is to maximize its total future reward by influencing the current actions based on the current state and estimated maximum reward. This reward is given as the potential reward from the weighted sum of the expected values ($E(x)$) from *all* future steps including the current state. The state-action combination to update the reward quality is given by:

$$Q : S \times A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

Each time the agent enters a state, it selects an action and observes the reward. The value of the reward determines the next state of the agent, and Q is updated accordingly, as to maximize the future potential. γ is a critical parameter (with range $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$) that allows the agent to assign rewards that arrive "quickly" with a higher value than other options. This function (γ) can help the algorithm to quickly arrive at a maximized reward, but at the cost of "exploration," as the agent will continue to seek the highest reward. In the case of self-driving cars or walking Nao robots [5], this can lead to the algorithm prematurely determining the "optimal" path or sequence of actions.

2.2 Well-Known Algorithms & Architectures

Below, the primary (well-known) algorithms and techniques are briefly discussed [25]. There are various other techniques and algorithms, though they are embedded (implicitly or optionally) within the following models:

2.2.1 Convolutional Neural Network

The primary algorithm used for this project is the convolution (in the *CNN*). The *CNN* uses a multilayering perception scheme and is bio-inspired from what was assumed a representation on how the brain works. *CNNs* are ideal for deep learning and computer vision problems, since they require minimal pre-processing. However, they do not innately have the ability to "remember," which is a limitation seen within this project (and mitigated by saving the training sets over many iterations). Furthermore, *CNNs* are often trained over GPUs, which made this project feasible, as training locally would require a substantial amount of processing (which ultimately becomes a problem with time and energy consumption).

2.2.2 Recurrent Neural Network

One method to solve the issues with "memory" is to introduce a *Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)*. The *RNN* implements a long-short term memory (*LSTM*) technique to process sequences of inputs based on its internal state (effectively memory). *RNNs* are usually used in combination with *CNNs* (*CNN encoder-RNN decoder*) for speech recognition problems but due to their simple "memory" ability, they are suitable for trivial reinforcement learning problems. An *RNN* was briefly attempted in the project though there were issues with the states. Therefore, this will be discussed more in the *Conclusion* section.

2.2.3 Stochastic Gradient Descent

Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) is an incremental (iterative) method for optimizing around a cost feature. As this project uses rewards/costs, it is ideal to use an optimization process. The stochastic convention refers to the technique of randomly selecting samples instead of sequentially processing in a linear manner. Most *DQN* processing models use *SGD* with *Q-Learning* so that the agent learns to avoid states that lead to poor rewards over the course of time. *SGD* is used with *Backprop* (see below) in order to prevent an issue related to "normal" gradient descent where the *global minimum* of the *error function* becomes stuck in a *local minimum* (and never finds the *global minimum*).

2.2.4 Backpropagation

Backpropagation (Backprop) is utilized in order to implement *Temporal Difference Learning*. *Backprop* is usually used in systems/networks where the gradient needs weights to be calculated in order to minimize output errors via feedback. Usually, *Backprop* is used in supervised learning for modeling internal representations for arbitrary mappings of the input to the output. Generally, the *cost* feature is called the "*loss function*" for *Backprop*, but they are ultimately synonymous.

2.3 Current Algorithms & Architectures

The following section discusses some of the currently researched algorithms and architectures. At the time of writing, these could be regarded as "State of the Art," though this term does not have a long shelf-life in AI.

2.3.1 Asynchronous Actor-Critic Agents

Asynchronous Actor-Critic Agents (A3C) is a newer algorithm (2016) that was also created by DeepMind [6]. This architecture has been claimed to be "essentially obsoleting DQN" [7] as it is faster, more robust, simpler to implement, and compatible with continuous action spaces. Furthermore, *DQNs* use a single agent and a single neural network for a single environment, whereas *A3C* utilizes a global network with multiple, parallel "workers" capable of having to interact with its own "copy" of the environment while having different hyperparameters (this is called *Asynchronous*).

Fig. 4: A3C general architecture with n workers [7].

The result is a large amount of speedup for training/task completion, as well as each agent having its own discrete, independent experience. The *Actor-Critic* portion is a value-iteration method (i.e., using *Q-learning*, *Policy Gradient*, or some other offline-policy) to estimate (and predict) a value function that shows, using probabilistic methods, the relative "goodness" of an action and distributes rewards. *A3C* uses *CNNs* with *LSTM* to process temporal dependencies [7].

Fig. 5: Learning speed comparison for DQN and the new asynchronous algorithms on five Atari 2600 games. [6].

In summary, a set of worker agents with their own networks and environments (with each worker running on a separate processor thread), collect experience from actions and rewards and updates the global parameters. This process repeats after each training set and the workers continually improve. Processing speed is greatly improved and the *A3C* is able to evaluate different experience/reward values simultaneously.

2.3.2 Progressive Neural Networks

Progressive Neural Networks (ProgNN) were created (DeepMind 2016) to solve the following challenge: accelerate learning via transfer when possible while avoiding *catastrophic forgetting* and solve K independent tasks at the end of training. It is well-known, especially for *CNNs*, that *ANNs* fail to create any useful memories or associations. This has been a problem through *DQNs* (even using *LSTM*) as “bad behaviors” can easily replace previously learned “good behaviors”. This is known as *catastrophic forgetting* since an agent might come to a conclusion that the best reward is to “do nothing” even after it completed tasks that provide far better rewards (this is especially common in self-driving car network design and is usually fixed by applying a negative reward function) [11].

One of the benefits of approaching this with *ProgNNs* is that they do not destroy the features learned on prior tasks which allow for better transfer learning. *ProgNNs* also do not assume that there are any relationships between tasks by creating a “column” that has independent weights (with random initialization) and each column is free to reuse, modify, or ignore the previously learned features based on lateral connections. This architecture is particularly well suited to solve discrete *Markov Decision Processes (MDPs)*.

Fig. 6: Depiction of a three column progressive network. The first two columns on the left (dashed arrows) were trained on task 1 and 2 respectively. The grey box labeled α represent the adapter layers. A third column is added for the final task having access to all previously learned features [11].

To compare to the human aspects of perception and cognition, some Gaussian noise is added to the system as a visual occlusion. The results of adding low-level visual noise were that by transitioning from a non-noisy game (i.e. Pong) to a noisy game required the network to relearn some processes, as it was not sufficiently tolerant to the added noise. Conversely, when transitioning from a noisy game to a “clean” game (no occlusions), all of the vision transfers were applicable to the new task. This might seem self-evident, but there is some value in observing that the networks that were initially in a noise-free environment had to “reassess” the spatiotemporal aspects of moving objects (a ball and paddle) due to insufficient observations, whereas this was not the case when transitioning to noise-free environments. This is similar to a human learning

to drive/operate in a rainy/foggy environment and then suddenly being asked to drive in a clear-view environment. DeepMind reported that utilizing *ProgNNs* allowed for “transfer percentages” of up to 491% over their baseline comparisons for different games. They were also able to employ “continual learning” which not only prevents “catastrophic forgetting” but also ensures that experiences and rewards continue to improve when possible [16].

Fig. 7: Example of learning curves for transfer learning between Pong and other games. The Prog2 is a two-column ProgNN, whereas the baseline implementations are single columns focusing on networks trained on either target or source tasks [11].

In order to verify and validate the results of *ProgNNs*, DeepMind recently exported their network design to a *Jaco* robot arm. The results give validation to the simulation environment, as the arm was able to implement transfer learning schemes and effectively “catch” objects [15].

Fig. 8: Google DeepMind demonstration of a ProgNN (with A3C) implementation on a *Jaco* robotic arm [15].

2.3.3 Ternary Neural Networks

It is commonly known that electrical signals in the brain occur as impulses. In order to better represent such impulse, a specific kind of neural networks were created call *Ternary Neural Networks (TNN)* or *Ternary Weight Networks (TWN)*. Biological neurons are gain elements because ion pumps convert chemical energy to electrical potential, which makes neurons active devices. To achieve this function with an electronic emulator, the artificial neuron should be able to provide energy for signal fan-out and propagation in multi-layer networks. To do this, *TWNs* have their weights constrained to three values, +1, 0, and -1 [13].

This “binary distribution” is more similar to how the brain interprets impulses. *TWNs* have stronger expressive

Fig. 9: Ternary discretization of neuronal activations and derivative approximation methods. The quantization function $\psi r(x)$ (a) together with its ideal derivative in (b) can be approximated by (c) or (d) [12].

abilities than the recently proposed binary precision counterparts. Furthermore, *TNNs* are usually created with FPGAs with fine-tuned accelerators, that resemble the “accelerators” that brain makes (Intelligent Architectures book, page 264). Combining the constrained weights and optimized hardware, the computational overhead is greatly reduced.

An example of an implementation called the GXNOR-Net is shown below. The results of the paper were between 97 and 99% accuracy for commonly used benchmarking suites (MNIST, SVHN). Another suitable approach to brain modeling is the GXNOR-Net is *event-driven*, which allows for the network to be “resting” prior to an event and is more similar to how the brain works for general processes.

Fig. 10: GXNOR-Net. In a GXNOR-Net, when both the pre-neuronal activation and synaptic weight are non-zero, the forward computation is required, marked as red. This indicates the GXNOR-Net is a sparse binary network, and most of the computation units can be switched off which reduces power consumption. The enable signal determined by the corresponding weight and activation acts as a control gate for the computation [12].

The computing archetype of the brain is not limited by the separation of memory and processing, serial execution, power inefficiency, and programming intensive issues of the

Fig. 11: Implementation of the GXNOR-Net example. By introducing the event-driven paradigm, most of the operations are efficiently kept in the resting state until the valid gate control signals wake them up. The signal is determined by whether both the weight and activation are non-zero [12].

von Neumann architecture. A group recently exploited the time-dependent electrical conductance resulting from the Ag mass migration due to the combined electrochemical and diffusion processes in a dielectric medium between two electrodes responding to an applied voltage to emulate the dynamics of ion channels in neurons. A Hebbian-like mechanism was implemented to program pseudo-memcapacitive synapses with this hybrid neuro-transistor, which was then used for associative learning and signal classification in a prototypical integrated capacitive switching neural network [14]. While not a *TNN*, this implementation covers the “time-driven” aspects of electrical signals from synapses and is appropriate for comparison.

3 THE HUMAN SIDE

To maintain consistency with “The Computer Side,” some brief comparisons are made to emphasise what is similar and dissimilar (lacking) between the brain and ANNs. The dissimilarities will be crucial to explore if better models that reflect human learning.

3.1 Parallel Processing

It should be no surprise that intelligent architectures like animal brains are capable of parallel processing. From an evolutionary standpoint, the brain needs to be able to respond quickly to environments with simultaneous stimuli while still meeting some goal (gathering resources, etc.), else it might die or receive a painful penalty. For simplicity and coherence, image processing and the Stroop effect are primarily discussed.

3.1.1 Stroop Effect

A simple method for testing (and explaining) the evidence of parallel processes is with a Stroop Test. This test often shows an observer a set of words that simultaneously have two meanings and can confuse the observer. The best example is when words are shown to the observer with a (in-)compatible representation (i.e. read the word “blue” when the color is yellow or vice versa). This is used in cognitive psychology to measure response time and accuracy related to interference [17].

Fig. 12: Integrate-and-fire dynamics of the dynamic pseudomemcapacitor (DPM). a) Scanning electron micrograph of the plan view of the integrated DPM, and a transmission electron micrograph of the cross-section. b) Charge-voltage relationship of the integrated DPM. The hysteresis loops reveal the volatile switching between the intrinsic parallel capacitor CP of the memristor and the series capacitor CS. c) Schematic representation of a biological neuron generating an action potential after receiving high-frequency post-synaptic inputs. d) The integrate-and-fire process of a DPM. e) Schematic of the neuro-transistor, consisting of a DPM integrated onto the gate of a MOSFET. f) Dynamics of the neuro-transistor integrate-and-fire process. The left panel shows a sequence of input spikes at high frequency ($20\mu\text{s}$ intervals, blue line), the potential of the series capacitor (black lines), and the axon membrane current (red line) indicated in e. In the right panel, identical pulses with $80\mu\text{s}$ intervals were applied, leading to a much slower firing rate [14].

The pre-frontal cortex is essential in a range of processes that are important for working memory. A critical mechanism for working memory function is the synchronization of pre-frontal cortex activity with activity in other brain regions. The pre-frontal cortex has long been implicated as a source of top-down signals that can influence processing in other cortical and sub-cortical brain regions. Given that the pre-frontal cortex represents rules and goals at multiple levels of abstraction, it is in an ideal position to influence processing in downstream brain regions [18].

3.1.2 Processing Speed

However, in terms of processing speed, two other components come into play. The posterior dorsolateral prefrontal cortex is tasked with creating appropriate rules for the brain to accomplish its current goal. For the Stroop effect,

Fig. 13: Example of a Stroop test. The colors and shapes have incompatible word assignments [17].

this involves activating the areas of the brain involved in color perception, but not those involved in word encoding. The anterior cingulate cortex selects appropriate responses and allocates attentional resources. These functions together suggest that with practice, the brain is capable of identifying and strategically inhibiting certain processes [19].

In comparing to "The Computer Side," we can consider an ANN that is tasked to "read" a set of words while also interpreting a color (simultaneously would need an RNN-CNN). An RNN can quickly interpret the word "blue" from a dictionary with little effort. A CNN would need a bit more effort in threshing out superfluous information, completing convolutions on an image, extracting the word, and then coming to a result. Therefore, the processing speed would obviously differ. One difference here is that networks can be designed to be independent, which would completely omit interference.

3.2 Multi-Modal Cues and Bayesian Models

Humans integrate visual and haptic information in a statistically optimal fashion. Here, "statistically optimal" is given with respect to optimality criteria, specifically the *maximum likelihood principle (MLE)* and the *Minimal Variance Principle (MVE)*. These are both flavors of the Bayes estimator. In cases in which both visual and haptic information are simultaneously triggered, the likelihood is charged with determining what stimulus is most likely given some observation and the weighted average of the variance is optimal. It turns out that the brain automatically employs Bayesian models. Similar to how our ANNs are set up, the brain does with a general "winner-takes-all" mechanism. In cases like the Necker cube a different mechanism (*Rivalry*; alternatively one or the other) occurs and *Suppression* occurs for certain cases of sensory dominance (e.g. look with both eyes through a tiny hole). If there are minor conflicts, the cues are integrated (not all cues are equally important and many cues may exist for a single percept). Essentially, all ANNs use Bayesian statistics for calculations and the brain implicitly (and effectively) uses them for prediction, estimation, expectation, and integration [20].

3.3 Neural Fields

Another method of modeling human processing speed particularly for decision making processes is with *Neural Fields (NF)*. The interesting properties of neural fields include being biologically plausible, demonstrating memory functions and decision making events, as well as being dynamic. While technically a representation of an RNN developed in cognitive psychology, *NFs* are able to be "extracted" (more like interpreted) using scanning and dyeing techniques [21]. NB: *V1* is the primary visual cortex and *OP* is orientation preference.

Fig. 14: *Left* Equilibrium disposition of saturated and sensitive synapses. Black circles represent cell bodies and dendrites. Synapses are indicated as saturated (solid) or sensitive (dashed) terminations of axons. Reciprocal connections between α -patches (patchy connections) form an hexagonal array. (Other connections, although shown as unidirectional, are also reciprocal.) A representative pair of connections from α -cells to the β -patch is displayed in the upper-and lower aspects of the figure. At the centre of the figure, saturated and sensitive synapses show the networks analogy to a Möbius-strip within a β -patch (macrocolumn). To the right, representative links from the central macrocolumn to cells at homologous positions in neighboring macrocolumns are indicated. *Right* "Like-to-like" saturated patchy connections map the same part of the surrounding cortical field onto homologous cell positions on the Möbius configuration within each macrocolumn, while at short range "like-to-like" saturated synaptic connections also form between homologous positions between local maps [22].

On the Möbius strip, spatial relationships of sensory representations maintain nearest-neighbour relations, and distances from singularities are associated with the distribution of conduction delay from surrounding cortex. Subsequent Hebbian-strengthened connections can bridge points with higher spatio-temporal correlations than accounted for by physical distance of separation in sensory space alone [22].

It has long been known that a macroscopic level, sensory inputs to, and motor outputs from, the cortex are arranged into topographic maps. Displaying these mappings (Fig.15) allows us to gauge the level of "goodness" in modeling the approximate results of a RNN by comparing the two (real and simulated).

3.4 Memory

As discussed, one of the largest problems with *ANNs* is their ability to "remember." While there are components (flash,

Fig. 15: 4 Simulated and real maps of orientation preference in V1. *Left*: Simulation. Colors of the spectrum, from red to violet, represent average OP of V1 neurons for slow-moving visual lines of orientation $0 - \pi$. Adjacent macrocolumns, of diameter approx $300 \mu\text{m}$ are set within an hexagonal frame (the patch system) with OP forming color wheels about OP singularities. Orientations and chiralities of the color wheels are arranged to approach a minimum total of angular disparity from mirror reflection of OP between each macrocolumn and its neighbours. *Right*: Real OP. Visualized in the tree shrew. Superficial patchy connections are demarcated in black by a selective stain. Scale of macrocolumns is approximate to that of the simulation [22].

HDDs) that memory can be stored in, mapping/recalling these memories appropriately for a task is challenging for an *ANN*. Five different memory types have been created to represent various functions and locations in the brain. Below, the five types of memory are discussed related to the brain along with a brief summary of their functions and usage [23]. A brief comparison is made towards computer-based implementation.

Fig. 16: Memory types in sagittal view of brain. [23].

3.4.1 Prospective Memory

Prospective memory holds reminders to perform future actions in specific circumstances (e.g., to place homework in a bag before going to class). Perceptual processes monitor the environment for the cue, retrieve the memory, and bring cognitive attention to the intended action. *Prospective memory* is located in the anterior prefrontal cortex of the brain and is supported by memory processes distinct from those supporting other types of memory.

3.4.2 Attentive Memory

Attentive memory holds conscious memories that can be freely attended to (i.e. goals, plans, and task-relevant items) and can be sustained for substantial periods of time (though simultaneously it is highly volatile and prone to frequent failures). *Attentive memory* has two complementary operations: focusing and filtering. *Attentive memory* is found in the ventrolateral and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and is involved with task switching.

3.4.3 Associative Memory

Associative memory holds a set of non-conscious links between manifestations of co-occurring stimuli. It is common to associate with the visual features of an item, but fail to associate with other attributes such as its name, limiting our ability to recall it ("I will recognize it when I see it"). Associative memory is located within the limbic system, in the perforant pathway of the hippocampus and is responsible for the automatic recording of attended experiences.

3.4.4 Episodic Memory

Episodic memory is the recollection of past events. A person may remember the experience of hearing sentences being read aloud; but forget details such as whether the voice was male or female or the specific order of the sentences. Located in the entorhinal cortex, these memories involve highly processed input from every sensory modality and inputs relating to ongoing cognitive processes. These memories improve over the course of aging as the brain becomes more developed (and obviously there are more episodes to recall).

3.4.5 Conceptual Memory

Conceptual memory can be described as a continuum between perceptions and abstractions. Perceptions such as a "bouncing sphere" give way to concepts such as a "ball" and so on. *Priming* occurs when suppression of certain brain areas short-circuit the processing of information, allowing the response to become more probable, which causes perceptions to become more abstract. *Conceptual memory* takes place in two areas of the brain, the perceptual region (posterior) and the executive region (prior), which makes this type of memory difficult to interpret (or replicate).

3.4.6 Brain vs Computer

As can be seen from the various functions of the memory types, some functionality and storage capacities are more challenging than others to replicate or emulate. Particularly, machines have major challenges in creating associations and concepts (i.e. challenges means currently impossible). Prospects, attention, and episodes are much easier for computers to handle, as they can be programmed with detailed state machines to trigger memory locations or continually hold them (cache, meta-data, etc.). When using GPUs or dedicated accelerators, computers are less prone to errors than humans. As the human mind is still not fully understood, modeling the processes for *conceptual* and *associative* memories will continue to be a challenge. However, it is not that we need to understand in detailed how these functions work, but rather, consider *what the goals of these memories are*. Besides, this is how the first ANNs were designed (from

a breakthrough perspective; recall, by cognitive scientists that had interest in computer science and not the other way around).

4 EXPERIMENT

4.1 ViZDoom - Project Overview

ViZDoom is a Doom-based AI Research Platform for Reinforcement Learning from Raw Visual Information. The goal is to create agents capable of playing the game using only visual feedback (by accessing and analyzing the screen buffer) and some limited scripting to allow "rewarding" certain actions such as picking up items or attacking monsters. This project seeks to implement and analyze the results of adding an A3C network to train the agents [24].

Fig. 17: Game play example for Doom.

4.1.1 Mechanics

ViZDoom primarily intended for research in machine visual learning, and deep reinforcement learning, in particular. It works by processing the screen buffer and returning visual information that can be used with neural networks. Various scenarios can be created depending on the information processing that the user wishes to conduct. Therefore, popular computer vision techniques such as color thresholding, semantic segmentation, labeling data (bounding boxes) and frame stacking are easy to implement.

Fig. 18: ViZDoom with color thresholded out and bounding boxes with labels around targets.

4.1.2 Default Network

The network has been initialized with default hyperparameters and layers. The network's task is to guide the "player" (agent) to achieve the highest score possible. In the default settings, the agent is rewarded simply for

killing demons. The agent initially has finite health and ammunition (100 health and 20 rounds). Accurate shots allow the agent to conserve ammunition, as the enemy demons can receive “chip damage” when being hit outside of a critical region. Furthermore, the agent can “conserve health” by identifying the target and eliminating it before the target can damage the agent. The default mode can be augmented to allow the agent to move around, collecting additional ammunition and health. Essentially, a high score is time dependent as the longer the agent is alive, the more opportunities it has to gain points.

The valid actions have some freedom in implementation. The agent can move forward, strafe, turn, or even walk backwards (which is not recommended as the additional states add nothing positive to the final score or performance and can actually cause the performance to decrease). Reward (and penalty) values need to be selected for each state and action for both the agent acting on the environment and vice versa. Intuitively, a penalty is given to the agent for taking damage or using ammunition and a reward is given for gaining health and defeating demons. To constrain the agent from moving arbitrarily, a penalty can also be applied for movement. To encourage quicker kills, a penalty can be added for each time-step.

4.1.3 Project Setup

ViZDoom is open-source and can be acquired at GitHub [24]. Simulation information is provided below.

TABLE 1: Simulation Environment.

Tool	Specification
Laptop	Acer Nitro 5
CPU	Intel i5-8300H CPU @ 4.0GHz
GPU	Nvidia GeForce GTX 1050, Intel UHD Graphics 630
OS	Ubuntu 16.04 LTS
ViZDoom	Release (1.1.7)
Python	Release (3.7.2)
CMake	Release (2.8)
GCC	Release (4.9)
Boost Lib	Release (1.54)
Torch	Release (Torch7)
Numpy	Release (v1.16.0rc2)

4.2 Metrics

Since this is ultimately a game, the metrics are related to the score. Specifically, the maximum average score and variance scores are analyzed for 200 epochs and 10 total runs. The goal is, of course, to obtain higher values for these scores. The traditional *RL* metric is maximizing the reward rate (the quicker the better) over time (epochs/trials). The higher the reward rate, the higher the performance of the network and better scores will be achieved.

4.3 Data Exploration

There are a number of data points that can be analyzed for the project. On the bare minimal implementation, the primary goal is to teach the agent that killing demons is good and dying is bad. Secondary criteria are that expending ammunition is bad (but necessary). Therefore the initial

goal is to create a map in which the agent can only turn (left or right) and shoot, to minimize the state space.

On a more sophisticated implementation, we can consider adding health and ammunition to the map that will allow the agent to survive for longer. This adds some complexity to the agent, as now it needs to learn if it is more beneficial to run to resources or eliminate enemies within a certain range. Furthermore, demons respawn at certain time intervals and at random locations (after a fixed distance) from the origin point.

4.4 Network Architecture

First, a simple network needs to be created for the “basic implementation.” This will require some computer vision techniques (grayscale, then scaling down, then stacking frames). Next, a series of *CNNs* in decreasing grid size and increasing filter size needs to be added. The activation layers could either be *ReLU*, *ELU* or *tanh*. The *batch normalization* will be paired with *ELUs* simply because the outputs are linear and can be negative. A *tanh* activation function could be used, but there is an issue with vanishing gradients and *ReLU*s are known for being susceptible to *Dead Neurons* (i.e., neurons that die during training and the weights will never update on that data point again). Finally, the output of the convolutions needs to be flattened, as the *FCs* are expecting a 1-D tensor (array) as an input. A visualization is shown below:

Fig. 19: Network architecture for a basic environment [26].

For the more sophisticated implementation (i.e. the agent has access to valid actions that can prolong the game), some slight modifications need to be completed making a *Deep Recurrent Neural Network (DRQN)*, which is a flavor of the *DQN*. The input image is fed to two convolutional layers, each which split the data into two streams. One stream flattens the output for an *LSTM* (the *RNN* portion) and the other stream feeds the data into an additional hidden layer which is used to categorize game features. During the training phase, both the *Q-learning* objectives and game features are trained together.

Fig. 20: Network architecture for a more advanced environment [27].

Finally, adding A3C needs the network to be modified slightly. Below, the general network is shown in which the FC layers are interconnected.

Fig. 21: Network architecture example for asynchronous methods [28].

4.5 Exploratory Visualization

The first step is to create an environment in which the agent and enemies will spawn. This environment will be a circular room with the agent beginning in the middle. This allows for enemies to spawn anywhere outside of approximately two meters from the agent. Below is an example of the created environment using SLADE.

Fig. 22: Circular environment for agent evaluation.

Fig. 23: Agent view in the circular environment.

Furthermore, we can analyze the results (input, frames) of the convolutions to see if network is performing as expected when testing the environments.

5 METHODOLOGY

5.1 Implementation

The implementation phases are completed using Anaconda (3.7; 64-bit) and the built in Jupyter Notebook feature.

Fig. 24: Convolution inputs and frames as an output of testing the environment.

The first step is to find appropriate training parameters for the network. The results of previous implementations were consulted along with trial-and-error methods [26] [27] [28]. The specific values are shown below:

```

Training the network

#Setting the training parameters:
batch_size = 1 #How many experience traces to use for each training step.
trace_length = 8 #How long each experience trace will be when training.
update_freq = 5 #How often to perform a training step.
gamma = .99 #Discount factor on the target Q-values.
startE = 1 #Starting chance of random action.
endE = 0.1 #Final chance of random action.
annealing_steps = 10000 #How many steps of training to reduce startE to endE.
num_episodes = 10000 #How many episodes of game environment to train network with.
pre_train_steps = 10000 #How many steps of random actions before training begins.
load_model = False #Whether to load a saved model.
path = "./dqn" #The path to save our model to.
h_size = 512 #The size of the final convolutional layer before splitting it into Advantage and Value streams.
max_episode_length = 50 #The max allowed length of our episode.
time_per_step = 1 #Length of each step used in gif creation.
summaryLength = 100 #Number of episodes to periodically save for analysis.
tau = 0.001
    
```

Fig. 25: Network training parameters.

In a modular manner, the A3C has its hyperparameters separate from the other windows. This allows for the performance of the agent using A3C to be compared to the rest of the network as a control variable.

```

A3C Parameters

max_episode_length = 300
gamma = .99 # discount rate for advantage estimation and reward discounting
s_size = 7056 # Observations are greyscale frames of 84 * 84 * 1
a_size = 3 # Agent can move Left, Right, or Fire
load_model = False
model_path = './model'
    
```

Fig. 26: A3C parameters.

After the network has been training parameters have been set, the testing phase begins. NB: *Q-learning* is off-policy and does not (usually) use an *epsilon greedy policy*, but the network does behave as if a greedy policy was used.

```

Testing the network

e = 0.01 #The chance of choosing a random action.
num_episodes = 10000 #How many episodes of game environment to train network with.
load_model = True #Whether to load a saved model.
path = "./dqn" #The path to save/load our model to/from.
h_size = 512 #The size of the final convolutional layer before splitting it into Advantage and Value streams.
max_episode_length = 50 #The max allowed length of our episode.
time_per_step = 1 #Length of each step used in gif creation.
summaryLength = 100 #Number of episodes to periodically save for analysis.
    
```

Fig. 27: Network testing parameters.

6 RESULTS

The agent was able to significantly improve its target metric scores and the reward function was able to approach the maximum value.

With the final selection of hyperparameters, the network was able to approach the ideal reward function after 20 trials. Steady state behavior is a bit lacking until after 60

```

Episode: 0 Total reward: 119.0 Training loss: 0.4769 Explore P: 0.9883
Episode: 1 Total reward: 129.0 Training loss: 0.8236 Explore P: 0.9757
Episode: 2 Total reward: 69.0 Training loss: 0.4909 Explore P: 0.9691
Episode: 3 Total reward: 53.0 Training loss: 0.3889 Explore P: 0.9640
Episode: 4 Total reward: 62.0 Training loss: 1.2403 Explore P: 0.9501
Episode: 5 Total reward: 134.0 Training loss: 0.0773 Explore P: 0.9455
Model Saved
Episode: 6 Total reward: 106.0 Training loss: 0.1471 Explore P: 0.9357
Episode: 7 Total reward: 57.0 Training loss: 0.3047 Explore P: 0.9304
Episode: 8 Total reward: 64.0 Training loss: 0.8023 Explore P: 0.9245
Episode: 9 Total reward: 115.0 Training loss: 0.4330 Explore P: 0.9141
Episode: 10 Total reward: 145.0 Training loss: 0.2257 Explore P: 0.9011
Model Saved
Episode: 11 Total reward: 57.0 Training loss: 0.0000 Explore P: 0.8960
Episode: 12 Total reward: 62.0 Training loss: 0.1748 Explore P: 0.8905
Episode: 13 Total reward: 47.0 Training loss: 0.4255 Explore P: 0.8864
Episode: 14 Total reward: 59.0 Training loss: 0.0544 Explore P: 0.8812
Episode: 15 Total reward: 82.0 Training loss: 0.0439 Explore P: 0.8741
Model Saved
Episode: 16 Total reward: 103.0 Training loss: 0.0156 Explore P: 0.8653
Episode: 17 Total reward: 53.0 Training loss: 0.0169 Explore P: 0.8607
Episode: 18 Total reward: 50.0 Training loss: 0.0082 Explore P: 0.8565
    
```

Fig. 28: Example of reward and training lose values per episode.

```

Mean Reward: 25.87 Total Steps: 77479 e: 0.876349000001
Mean Reward: 29.7 Total Steps: 80449 e: 0.862984000001
Mean Reward: 30.84 Total Steps: 83533 e: 0.849106000001
Mean Reward: 34.07 Total Steps: 86940 e: 0.833774500001
Mean Reward: 36.39 Total Steps: 90579 e: 0.817399000002
Mean Reward: 33.12 Total Steps: 93891 e: 0.802495000002
Mean Reward: 35.4 Total Steps: 97431 e: 0.786565000002
Mean Reward: 32.98 Total Steps: 100729 e: 0.771724000002
Mean Reward: 39.89 Total Steps: 104718 e: 0.753773500002
Mean Reward: 43.53 Total Steps: 109071 e: 0.734185000002
Mean Reward: 43.16 Total Steps: 113387 e: 0.714763000002
Mean Reward: 47.85 Total Steps: 118172 e: 0.693230500003
Mean Reward: 48.49 Total Steps: 123021 e: 0.671410000003
    
```

Fig. 29: Example of mean reward value increasing over time.

trials, meaning the policy gradient and epsilon functions need improvement. There are nearly 100 options to chose from in these categories, so the results are sufficient for the project.

Fig. 30: Reward value over time (trials, epochs).

Below, a table is shown to demonstrate the final scores of the agent as well as tendencies to collect/expend health and ammunition while the network is improving. Training is quite slow using only the CPU with PyTorch/ TensorFlow, so an instance on AWS EC2 was used to speed up training (GPU implementation, free-tier).

TABLE 2: Scores for 200 training epochs (10 runs) with their metrics.

Metric	Trial / Score						
	1	2	3	...	198	199	200
mavg_score	107	94	135	...	318	213	357
var_score	892	772	2032	...	13895	20867	17789
mavg_ammun_left	18	23	27	...	27	13	22
mavg_kill_counts	1	1	2	...	16	10	20
mavg_collect_health	0	1	0	...	3	6	4
mavg_collect_weapon	1	1	1	...	2	2	2
mavg Lose_health	85	89	88	...	95	92	92
mavg_use_ammun	11	9	12	...	20	34	23
mavg_collect_ammun	0	7	17	...	29	16	8

7 DISCUSSION

7.1 Limitations of Reinforcement Learning

One of the critical arguments surrounding reinforcement learning is “humans can learn new tasks relatively quickly” as where networks need to complete upwards of millions of simulations to achieve any meaningful results. For games, this means the agent can fail and die repeatedly without ever giving any consideration (no penalty) to it (again, a lack of cognition, not that it matters here). If the goal is to model how humans learn simple or complex skills, on the surface level it would appear that reinforcement learning does a poor job of explaining how skills are acquired. Thus, reinforcement learning receives criticism that it requires too many resources and too much time (training) to learn new skills.

However, giving consideration to transfer learning, I would disagree. Recalling from what is known from “Intelligent Architectures,” we see that humans continue to learn and improve skills overtime, even in a subtle or passive manner. Furthermore, if a skill is used enough, an “accelerator” is created in the structure of the brain to allow this task (and similar ones) to be quickly repeated without thought. Humans become capable of enacting “auto-pilot” for many tasks, unaware of what or how they are completing them. The human brain also assigns information that has repeated exposure to the individual to a long-term working memory (recall associative and episodic memory as described previously). Furthermore, AI is currently able to gain such improvements without access to any “conceptual memory” that the brain has when implementing transfer learning.

In fact, I would state that humans do not learn skills relatively fast at all, even if it is the “first attempt.” Consider when someone is learning to drive a car. They already have the *concept* of what a car is. They can already understand most of the rules (supposed to be a safety requirement), they can understand the road signs and lights, as well as a general idea of how the vehicle operates (pedals, results of acceleration and turning, etc.). In this sense, a human has already been learning “how to drive” long before ever sitting behind the wheel. With this passive experience building up over 14 to 18 years, perhaps humans are not that good at transfer learning as we like to think when comparing to neural networks.

Fig. 31: Richard Feynman teaching courses at CalTech on optics. [29].

One of the most influential physicists of all time, Richard Feynman, once stated that his students at CalTech (which must have been brilliant to be there) came to the conclusion

that teaching is only effective if the student already “almost knows the subject material.” In his textbook, *The Feynman Lectures on Physics*, he famously quotes Gibbons in his preface that: “The power of instruction is seldom of much efficacy, except in those happy dispositions where it is almost superfluous” [29]. Learning embedded systems at TU Eindhoven is no different, as graduate students have already “learned how to learn” for the courses (and it is evident with those students that have not).

8 CONCLUSION

8.1 Reflection

Given what has been explored, it might appear that reinforcement learning (particularly deep learning) is not (currently) sufficient in being able to create a computational model of human learning and understanding. However, if an approximation is desired (which is usually the goal of ANNs), there are several steps being taken in the proper direction. In terms of the project, I felt like this was a decent experiment to explore the A3C framework and provide a stepping stone for completing future work (improving the current network, integrating other algorithms/techniques, etc.).

In particular, solving issues of “catastrophic forgetting” is a crucial step for improving the performance of ANNs. More importantly, being able to *do something* by applying transfer learning will make all of the difference in research for AI and even provide some cues for the direction of AGI. For a machine to be able to replicate and transfer any learning ability, they would be able to integrate into normal, human-like tasks in daily life. So much that the “average person” would not be able to distinguish between human behavior and machine behavior. I think that AI is just a few breakthroughs away from being able to have a much larger scale effect on robotics (human-robot social interaction and collaborative robotics).

In the question “will agents ever have consciousness?”, we can consider the criteria that Bostrum et al. have provided: *sentience* and *sapience* [30]. *Sentience* is the capacity for phenomenal experience or qualia (such as the ability to feel pain and suffering). *Sapience* is a set of capacities associated with higher intelligence with emphasis on self-awareness or being reason-responsive. It is not too difficult for an agent that has *associative and conceptual memories* to be able to conclude that it is self-aware. Being able to interpret suffering through individuality is a different story though. It could be able to draw associations on “what” suffering is (and even be able to “label” such events and emotional responses from animals) but this does not mean that it will be able to “feel” the same way [34]. Possibly, given enough experience and memories, an agent could become dissatisfied with receiving “penalties” from poor actions. Were this the case, it might be a step in the right direction to meet these criteria (assuming they are sufficient), or at least instill the idea of “empathy” for machines. Human-like thought portends predictable complications, and as such, leads to interesting values for morals, ethics, and individual experience. This is a starting point for developing the “proto-self” and furthermore, allows us to consider what a

“theory of mind” looks like not only for an agent but also better insights for human consciousness.

8.2 Improvement/Future Work

The most interesting direction that ANNs could go with RL would be to develop *associative* and *conceptual memories* for machines. This may allow them to finally gain enough frameworks to be able to make independent decisions that appear as arbitrary as human decision-making processes. Much of the analysis of human decisions can be approximately using Bayesian statistics, MDP/POMDPs, or other probabilistic and/or deterministic methods. However, there are many aspects of being human that are highly dynamic/stochastic in which these approximations fail or are inappropriate. It might be worth investigating not on “how the human mind/brain works” but rather continue attempting to model human behavior and translate that from some inputs to outputs for a machine. Since the initial neural networks were sufficiently “bio-inspired” while being absolutely trivial (and inaccurate), it makes sense to continue applying “what we know” when completing new functional and quality requirements for artificial behavior. “Strong AI” will require that the agents can have intentionality in their decision making processes.

Improvement for this particular project should include better hyperparameter selection, a better epsilon/decay function, and integration of more of the techniques discussed (*ProgNN*) [31]. Furthermore, an FPGA or ASIC implementation of a TNN or TWN would be interesting as well, as combined, we would get closed to an architecture that was created specifically for artificial agents (like the “neural substrate” and “embodiment” practical starting points from the Intelligent Architectures course). Occasionally, cognitive scientists look at the human-computer analogy with the thought that a computer is “a mind with no body,” since (those older) computers were unable to move freely, regardless of their peripheral components. Or maybe, we do not even need a physical interpretation and a “virtual environment” will be sufficient for emulating agents.

Due to the dissimilarity to the rest of the project and report, research regarding another bio-inspired neural network approach was omitted until this point. Ideally, we can create some form of network that has the biological building blocks that organic life has such as hormones, neuro-transmitters, and opiates. *Neuroevolution*, or the artificial evolution of neural networks, is being created to meet these purposes by utilizing memory to apply continuous reinforcement learning for raw video images and streams [32]. Another topic is using neural connectomics for automatic discovery of cell types and microcircuitry. Using connectomics, we can understand how these circuits and cell type distributions can be used to create better neural networks [33]. Both topics focus on the realm of visual processing with inference and predictions. However, they still rely on Bayesian statistics and probabilistic modeling that are fed backward into the networks. Regardless, finding a practical implementation with the other discussed topics might provide more direction (or convergence) on the validity of creating the ideal neural network.

Fig. 32: UL-ERL Architecture. The standard neuroevolutionary RL approach is augmented by an adaptive compressor that transforms high-dimensional observations into a compact code which serves as input to the evolving recurrent neural network controllers. At each generation the compressor is trained on observations generated by the evaluated controllers, using unsupervised learning. As the compressor improves, the controllers are provided with increasingly informative features, and, in turn, they provide new data for the compressor to improve the features. [32].

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